

A Grasping Task with Soft Objects to Understand Visuo-Haptic Cross-modal Effects

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Abstract. The perception of an object’s compliance involves several senses including vision and touch. Several studies have shown cross-modal interactions between the two modalities. However, the integrative mechanisms underlying this process remain unclear. We therefore aim to explore the mechanisms involved in the visuo-tactile perception of compliance, namely how tactile and visual information are integrated and merged together. But one of the difficulties encountered in visuo-haptic studies of compliance is the generation of conflict between the two modalities through the presentation of a visual deformation that differs from the haptic deformation. To overcome this problem, we propose to create a behavioral task using a virtual environment. First, we created a set of deformable objects that are specifically designed to be embedded in a virtual reality environment and we performed a preliminary psychological task in which participants were asked to report the object perceived as the most compliant between a pair based on haptic feedback only. The results showed that soft objects are more difficult to discriminate than hard objects. In future experiments, we plan a visuo-haptic grasping task in virtual environment using similar silicone cubes.

Keywords: Compliance Perception · Tangible objects · Cross-modal effects.

1 Introduction

The material properties of everyday objects vary considerably and recognising these properties is essential for object identification and classification [6, 3]. One important material property is compliance. In psychophysics, compliance studies seek to determine the extent to which a surface or object is perceived as deformable by the participant [2]. Multiple studies have shown that the perception of compliance requires processing both haptic and visual informations [4, 5], but the mechanisms involved in this process are still not completely understood. To better understand the integration of visual and haptic cues involved in compliance perception and the weight assigned to each modality by human perception, we intend to create a grasping task involving a sensory conflict using a virtual environment. In our study, participants will compress within their bare hand objects of varying compliance, estimate the compliance those objects, and evaluate how much the visual deformation differs from the haptic deformation. In the virtual environment, we aim to modify the visual properties of the object without affecting their

Fig. 1. **a.** Example of a soft object with embedded sensor. **b.** Results of the psychophysical experiment : proportion averaged across participants for which the comparison object is considered to be stiffer than the reference, based on the difference in shore level (median and interquartile range). **c.** Example of force data recorded during one trial.

physical properties [1, 7]. To that end, we needed a set of compliant objects that would be usable in a virtual reality environment.

In this preliminary study, we designed a set of deformable objects that could be used our next experiment, we evaluated how differently compliant they feel, and we collected force contact data that will be used to drive the visual deformation of the objects in the VR environment.

2 Materials and Methods

The objects with embedded sensors are composed of six silicone cubes ($H \times W \times L = 30 \times 35 \times 55 \text{ mm}^3$), six force sensing resistors (FSR03CE) connected to a microcontroller (Arduino Uno R3). The overall system is optimised to collect data at a sampling rate of 70 Hz. The set of flexible objects was created using *Ecoflex*TM silicone . To achieve different elasticities, we adjusted the mixing ratio of the two-part elastomer EcoFlex. Their Shore hardness was measured using a Shore 00 durometer (see Fig. 1a.).

A 2-alternative forced-choice paradigm was used. In each trial, participants were presented simultaneously the standard stimulus and one of the four comparison stimuli. The standard stimulus has a haptic compliance of 38 in Shore 00 hardness level and the comparison stimuli have compliance of 26, 32, 44 and 47 in Shore 00 hardness level. Participants were asked to compress each stimulus between their thumb and their index finger. Through this gesture, they had to haptically judge which stimulus they perceived as the more compliant. Each pair of standard and comparison stimuli was presented 8 times in pseudo-random order (32 trials in total = 1 standard x 4 comparison x 8 repetitions).

3 Results

We conducted an experiment to test how accurately participants could compare compliant objects designed for a future VR study. Five persons (2 males, 3 females) were recruited to participate in this experiment. The average ratio of correctly picked objects

was 0.91 ± 0.1 (see Fig. 1b.) showing that the task presented some challenge. Interestingly, the results show that people easily felt the difference in compliance when comparison objects were more rigid than the reference but found it more challenging when comparison objects were flexible. We also measured the force applied on the objects during each trial (see Fig. 1c.). The contact forces measured will be used to drive the visual deformation of the compliant objects by using the spring model of compliance.

4 Discussion

In this study, we produced a set of silicone objects with controlled differences in compliance and embedded pressure sensors. We showed that performance was good but not perfect for objects softer than the reference while objects that were harder than the reference were easily discriminated. The next step would be to refine the shore values of objects in order to make harder objects less easy to discriminate. With these manufactured objects, we will explore how participants perceive visuo-haptic compliance by altering the deformability of visual objects in a virtual environment. The visual and haptic information of deformation will be either consistent or inconsistent (visual information could indicate an object with identical or different compliance than the haptic one). We will test whether the cross-modal effect is impacted by the visual object being softer or harder than the haptic one. The force measurements taken during our preliminary experiment will be used to implement the deformation of the virtual objects.

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